

Dataset Bingo (v2)

Dataset Bingo was developed as a hands-on activity for an introductory data workshop for graduate students, faculty, and staff. The activity was designed as a way to include a wide variety of participants at different stages of their career and with different levels of experience evaluating and working with datasets. Dataset Bingo can be used as a fun way to introduce participants to good practices in data documentation and data sharing.

Resources

What do you need to play Dataset Bingo?

Included

- Printable bingo cards for in-person play in two formats:
 - PDF file - the easiest to print, formatted for US-letter sized paper.
 - Excel file - if you'd like to customize the text or need to adjust print settings.
- [Online bingo cards](#) for virtual play
- A list of datasets you can use to play the game of varying quality and formats

Not included

- An introductory lecture that covers data documentation and data sharing best practices
- Prizes for the winners (optional)
- Bingo markers/daubers (optional)

Instructions

How the game is played, set up, and winning criteria.

What is bingo?

Bingo is a matching game played across squares laid out in a grid. Winning requires creating a straight unbroken line of matches across the grid (row, column, or diagonal) which is called a "bingo".

Dataset Bingo uses a 5 x 5 grid with a total of 25 squares, so a line of 5 matches is required to win. The center square, which has an icon of a floppy disk, is a "wild card" square that all players get to count as a match automatically. This increases the chance of a bingo as four of the possible routes to win have been reduced to only needing four matches instead of the normal five. However, bingo is a game of chance and a win is never guaranteed.

The squares in Dataset Bingo describe various characteristics of datasets. Players try to find matches between the text in their card's squares and the dataset chosen by or assigned to them. This kit comes with 20 bingo cards. The text in the squares is the same for every card but the location of the text on the cards is randomized so that each card is unique.

Setup

After the introductory lecture, pass out a bingo card to each player. Next split the class into groups of 2-4 players and assign a dataset to each group (alternatively, have them pick a dataset). Each group should have access to at least one computer to allow them to examine the dataset. Most of the datasets included in this kit can be viewed in a browser and do not need to be downloaded to be evaluated, but a few of them will require the downloading and opening of files.

Evaluation and discussion

Groups should be encouraged to discuss and evaluate their dataset together as all the bingo cards have the same criteria. Players should mark the squares that match their dataset in some way (such as making an X across the matching square, using a dauber, etc). If a student is uncertain if they have a match they should confer with the instructor who is the final judge on if a criteria is a fit.

Winning

When a student gets a bingo (a straight line of 5 matching squares) the instructor should check that the dataset matches each of the winning squares. The instructor should use their best discretion when judging a match and can use moments of doubt as to discuss why a dataset may or may not match a bingo criteria.

If giving out prizes you should plan on having at least one bingo for every 3 to 4 players (roughly one per group).

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Licenses

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Attribution

No attribution is required to reuse this activity. However citation is recommended using the DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17297232](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17297232)

Credits

Dataset Bingo was developed by Jen Ferguson, Megan O'Donnell, and Isaac Wink.

Dataset Bingo is based on [DMP Bingo - the good, the bad, the ugly \(v.2\)](#) by Megan O'Donnell.

Thank you to the Midwest Data Librarian Symposium 2025 attendees who played the game and provided valuable feedback as well as datasets for evaluation!

Appendix

Change log

V2: updates were made to bingo squares based on feedback from MDLS25; example dataset list updated to include more variety of sources; general cleanup and formatting

Bingo square criteria

1. Authorship is clear
2. Confusing or undefined abbreviation
3. Consistent file names
4. Contains sensitive information
5. Data file(s) open
6. Data is in open formats
7. Dataset is complete
8. Dataset is easy to cite
9. Documentation is adequate
10. Excel files lack formulas or macros
11. File names contain spaces or special characters
12. Files are organized
13. *Free parking*
14. Has a persistent identifier (e.g. DOI)
15. Has documentation
16. Has license/use statement
17. Has recognizable file extensions
18. Meaningful file names
19. Observations are in rows, variables are in columns
20. One table per spreadsheet
21. Origins and methodology are clear

22. Related outputs are cited or linked
23. Relationship between files are clear
24. Special equipment or tools are noted
25. Variables are understandable